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Socio-Economic Status and Associate Problems of the Tribals: A Case Study of a Village in Kurung Kumey District of Arunachal Pradesh

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Abstract: Hiya is a Nyishi tribal village located in the Nyapin block of Kurung Kumey district, Arunachal Pradesh. The present study slots in the socio-economic conditions and associate problems of the Nyishi tribal villagers of Hiya. This study tries to highlight various aspects of socio-economic structure like age-sex structure, marital status, educational structure, economic status etc. It also attempts to explore the problems faced by the tribal villagers like low income, lack of drinking water, low rate of literacy, transportation problem, etc. The study aims at suggesting ways how to overcome their social constraints in receiving proper facility.

Keywords: Social Constraints, Tribal Livelihood, Regional Attributes, Demographic Structure, Settlement Features, Socio-Economic Activities.

Introduction

Socio-economic condition means an economic and social combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to

others; based on income, education and occupation (Bhattacharya 2014, 1). The poor socio-economic condition of tribal villagers in Hiya is caused by its physiographic condition and lack of knowledge about development programmes of the government. This paper attempts to provide the data structure and reasons of poor socio-economic condition of Hiya tribal villagers and some suggestions to overcome these persistent problems.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. To understand the social and economic condition of the tribal villagers;
- ii. To evaluate their livelihood patterns;
- iii. To highlight their demographic structure, settlement features, economic activities; and
- iv. To explore the myriad problems and prospects of the study village.

Universe of Area

The universe of present study is Nyishi tribe in Kurung Kumey district of Arunachal Pradesh. But the model of study is Hiya village, located in Nyapin sub-division of Kurung Kumey district of central Arunachal Pradesh. Hiya, the largest village (in terms of area and population) of Kurung Kumey district is located in the extreme eastern part of the Nyapin circle, one of the oldest administrative circles of the state, with whom a status of small town was declared in the same name in 1953. The village has a population of more than 710 souls belong to 180 families/households as per the recent electoral rolls of 2011 (Ramya 2014). This excludes the population below 18 years of age.

In fact, the Hiya village is the blend of two villages i.e. Hiya-I and Hiya-II and two adjoining sub-villages i.e. Lumtey and Yarda. Hiya, once a single village was bifurcated into two villages in the year 2001 where the adjoining sub-villages Lumtey and Yarda shifted to Hiya-I and Hiya-II respectively. The village has now one government aided newly upgraded secondary school, one centrally sponsored

primary school under Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) and two pre-primary community schools. The administrations of the village are run under Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) with 2 Anchal Samiti Members (ASMs) and 8 Gram Panchayat Members (GPMs). Besides, the village too has 2 Head Gaon Burahs (HGBs) with few numbers of Gaon Burahs (GBs). The mosaic of these two combinations looks after the administrations of the village.

Map 1: Arunachal Showing Kurung Kumey District

Map 2: Kurung Kumey District Showing Nyapin Sub-Division

Map 3: Location of the Study Area (Hiya Village)

Source: <https://www.google.com/earth/>

Methodology Applied

As this study is based on sample survey, the majority of the data was collected from the villagers through interview with the help of questionnaires. The component of the age group for the study was 18 years old and above. Besides, data was collected from block development office at Nyapin.

Age-Sex Structure

Age-sex structure is one of the key parameters by which socio-economic status of villagers can be measure (Chandana 1996). The composition of population according to age and sex is formally known as age-sex structure. It is one of the most commonly method for analysing age composition. It varies from place to place depending upon the state of demographic transition. In the context of Hiya village, the percentage of younger age group is higher than that of adult age group. This means the dependency ratio in this tribal village is also high. The age-sex structure of the village also indicates high birth rate, low rate productive population, low rate of per capital income among the villagers.

Table No. 1: Age-Sex Structure of Hiya Village

Age Group	Male		Female	
	Population	Percentage	Population	Percentage
18-20	127	39.08	154	40.00
21-30	57	17.54	78	20.26
31-40	52	16.00	53	13.77
41-50	45	13.85	36	9.35
51-60	27	8.30	35	9.09
61 and Above	17	5.23	29	7.53
Total (710)	325	100.00	385	100.00

Source: Block Level Statistics of Kurung Kumey District, 2011.

Figure 1: Male and Female Population of Hiya Village

Marital Status

Marital status is an essential feature in the study of the condition of social structure of any given society. In the study village, marital status is divided into three divisions i.e. married, unmarried, and widow. The percentage of married female is higher than that of married male. Even the percentage of unmarried female is again more than unmarried male.

Table No. 2: Marital Status of Hiya Villagers

Categories	Married		Unmarried		Widow
	Male	Female	Male	Female	
No. of Persons	186	292	90	131	11
Total	478		221		11

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 2: Marital Status of Hiya Village

Educational Structure

A person who can read and write with understanding of any language is taken as literate while a person who can merely read but can't write is illiterate. It is not necessary that a person who is literate should have received any formal education or should have passed any minimum educational standard. In Hiya village, 74.10 % peoples are literate where as 25.90 % peoples are illiterate. Due to the superstition and cultural barrier the rate of female literacy is lower than the male counterpart.

Table No. 3: Educational Structure of Hiya Village

Categories	Literate		Illiterate	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
No. of Persons	371	155	72	112
Total	526		184	

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 3: Educational Structure of Hiya Village

Table No. 4: Literacy Status of Hiya Village

Educational Category	Primary	Middle	Secondary	Higher Sec.	Others
No. of Persons	34	204	189	68	31

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 4: Literacy Status of Hiya Village

Occupational Structure

Occupation is a medium through which one family spends their livelihood. In the study village, 38.73 % people are non-workers whereas main-workers and marginal-workers accounts for 37.18% and 24.08% respectively. So, this figure indicates higher rate of dependency which reflect a negative socio-economic aspect of the villagers.

Table No. 5: Occupational Structure of Hiya Village

Workers	Main-Workers	Marginal-Workers	Non-Workers
No. of Persons	264	171	275

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 5: Occupational Structure of Hiya Village

Income Structure

Per capita income is one of the central factors to perceive the G.D.P. of any particular region. Income of an individual and his/her standard of living closely related to one another. In the village, 83 (46.11%) family lies below poverty line (BPL) category. Most of the family is engaged with primary activities like agriculture, fishing, occasional hunting, forest gathering and horticulture.

Table No. 6: Income Structure of Hiya Village

Income Structure (in Rs./Month)	Below 2000	2000-5000	5000-8000	Above 8000
No. of Family (180)	83	27	45	25

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 6: Income Structure of Hiya Village (in Rs. /Month)

Sanitation Facility

Sanitation of a place relates to the health condition of people of that place. Poor tribal family does not get the facility because of lower income. The people who dwell in traditional houses have no sanitary system. But in case of modern houses, the people have the sanitation facilities in their houses. Of the total 180 households, only 46 (25.55%) households/families has proper sanitation in their houses whereas 134 (74.45%) does not have proper sanitation facility.

Table No. 7: Sanitation Facility of Hiya Village

No. of Family (180)	
Available	Not Available
46	134

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 7: Sanitation Facility of Hiya Village

Housing Conditions

The housing condition and the place of residence is an indicator of the quality of life as it is a core component of a human life. People having high income never live in a slum. So, the economic condition of the villagers, frankly, controls the housing conditions in the village. Most of the people 148 (82.22%) have traditional houses having the roof of straw or tin sheets. These houses only have maximum of two or three rooms. Some people 24 (13.34%) have semi-modern houses. The people who are engaged in tertiary sector have the modern houses 8 (4.44%) as their income is higher than the other villagers.

Table No. 8: Housing Condition of Hiya Village

Housing Structure	Traditional	Semi-Modern	Modern
No. of Family (180)	148	24	8

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 8: Housing Condition of Hiya Village

Electricity Facility

Electricity is the most essential feature of almost every human society in the contemporary era. In the village, almost every house has electricity connected. Of the total households, 174 (97%) households have electricity connection whereas only 6 (3%) households don't have electricity connection as they are located in the remotest periphery of the village.

Table No. 9: Electricity Facility of Hiya Village

Electricity Facility	Have	Have Not
No. of Family (180)	174	6

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 9: Electricity Facility of Hiya Village

Source of Drinking Water

Safe drinking water is the most essential feature for healthy human life. As the climate of Hiya village ranging from moderate to chilly cold, there is a scarcity of drinking water during winter season, most specifically during December-March every year. Most of the households, 163 (90.56%) take water from tap through a pipeline connected to water tank. Some households, 17 (9.44%) directly exploit

the river/stream for their need of water. Natural flowing waters from rivers/streams such as Hote, Paya, Rayi and Dadh are also used for domestic usages.

Table No.10: Source of Drinking Water of Hiya Village

Source of Drinking Water	Tap	River/stream
No. of Family (180)	163	17

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 10: Source of Drinking Water of Hiya Village

Medical Facility

The Nyishi tribal villagers of Hiya depend on the government aided hospital for their medical facility. The nearest government hospital (Tadar Tang Community Health Centre) is situated in Nyapin at a long distance of about 18-19 kms from village. However, the village has one health sub-centre but without any medical staff and medicine. A large section of the villagers depend on the government hospital for treatment of various illnesses since they don't have high income to look for private hospitals and clinics.

Irrigational Facility

Irrigation is required only for about 4 months during summer season for agricultural purpose. In the village, farmers mostly depend on naturally flowing river/stream waters for irrigational purpose. About

84.44% households have proper irrigational facility whereas about 28 (15.56%) households are yet to get proper irrigational facility.

Table No. 11: Irrigational Facility of Hiya Village

Irrigational Facility	Have	Have Not
No. of Family (180)	152	28

Source: Fieldwork

Figure 11: Irrigational Facility of Hiya Village

Some Constraints of the Village

Some of the key constraints being faced by Nyishi tribal villagers of Hiya may be summed up as follows:

- 1.The major constraint of the village is the low income of the tribal people. Since their income is low due to constraints in agricultural production. It is not sufficient for them to live a healthy and prosperous life.
- 2.Electricity is not entirely distributed in the houses of the villagers. Some of the houses are yet to see the electricity being lighted in their houses.
- 3.Many of the houses don't have any sanitary facility. This led to frequent illnesses of the villagers.
- 4.The housing condition in the village is very poor. Most of the people still dwell in traditional houses.

5. The village does not have good medical facility. The only good government hospital is located far away at a distance of about 18-19 kms from village.
6. Floods from rivers/streams during agricultural season cause irregularity of irrigation in the village.
7. Poverty is yet another major crisis of the village. About 83 (46.11%) family lies below poverty line (BPL) category.

Some Suggestions and Prospects of Study

To surmount the constraints of the villagers, following prospects may be suggested:

1. The government should take exceptional steps to do away with the frequent flood and sedimentation during the agricultural period which hamper the irrigation.
2. Proper sanitation strategy should be developed with the help of government and non-governmental agencies to content with improper sanitation in the village.
3. Housing conditions should be improved so that people could improve their standard of living too.
4. The existing health sub-centre in the village should be improved properly so that villagers could make use of the available medical facilities. The village also needs a doctor and some medical staffs in the sub-centre.
5. To increase the literacy status among the villagers necessary measure should be taken up with the proper implementation of Right to Education Act, 2009.
6. An adequate credit facility should provide to the poor tribal farmers so as to raise their agricultural productivity.
7. Irrigation systems have to be developed well, so that it can help the agriculture.

8. Self-help groups should undertake to perk up the socio-economic condition of the poor tribal villagers.

Conclusion

The entire discussion in this study helps to give almost complete idea about the demographic, social and economic structure of this Nyishi tribal village, Hiya. The villagers are facing numerous troubles like poverty, low income, female illiteracy, lack of proper sanitation, etc. These constraints can be eradicated with the help of diverse plans and programmes through the government authorities. Likewise, the benevolence of the dwellers of the Hiya village can advance the socio-economic condition of the tribal villagers. As an ultimate observation, therefore, it can be said that this study provides an exceptional prospect to explore the status and socio-economic condition of Nyishi tribal villagers of Hiya and the myriad problems and prospects of their development.

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